

ISic1645

I.Sicily inscription 1645

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object

painted rock face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Catacomba di San Giovanni

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [] □ Auxentius His
2. panus patria ep(iscopus) Rotdon
3. iacet hichuc et a[d]iuro vos qui legi
4. tistes [---]
- 5.
6. petite q[uo]
7. d acce[ptum]

Apparatus

Text after Ferrua 1940 with slight changes

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284570

EDR 073713
EDCS 12700073

Bibliography

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Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.82

Ferrua, A 1940. Nuovi studi nelle catacombe di Siracusa. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 17: 43-81. At 45 no.1

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